

24 September 2025

Press release

On September 9th 2025, the CST4ALL project hosted its project closing event in Brussels, Belgium. The event was open to both in-person and online participants from around the world. The event was hosted by ESTELA with contributions from all project partners, with 75 in-person and online participants. The event was critical in summarizing project results and also reflecting the alignment of project results with EU priorities and CST-IWG activities. Representatives from the European Commission, including project officer Charles-Andre Lemarie, industry and renewable energy associations were present in discussion to contribute to the future discussions of CST technology. The event was opened and chaired by project coordinator, Peter Heller from DLR. He reiterated the CST4ALL project objectives which includes monitoring and supporting the CSP Implementation Group, to enable cooperation across sectors covered by the SET Plan/ETIPs from an industrial/market and R&D perspective and to maximize project outcomes and impacts to address Green Deal Challenges. The event included a future outlook from the European Commission, and continued with an update of the Concentrated Solar Thermal Technologies Implementation Working Group (CST/IWG) activities. These updates were critical in understanding how best to align CST Technologies within industry, project and cross-collaboration networks within the CST and RE community. The event later continued with a categorization of EU funded CST projects, reflecting the investment potentials of countries across Europe and the scope of work according to CST-SET Plan priorities. Insights from the R&I and industry workshops were reflected and the SSH (Social Science and Humanities) aspects were also detailed, bridging cross-cutting needs for improved energy and climate strategies and technology implementation. The event ended with a round-table discussion addressing EU cross technology collaboration. The following are key highlights from the distinguished speakers and their presentations:

Marina Montero Carrero, Policy Officer addressed the future of CST within the Horizon Europe (2021-2027) agenda, Clean Industrial Deal implications to support the Affordable Energy Action Plan and the new efforts towards the Electrification Action Plan in support of CST Technologies. She indicated that project funding in support of the technology and the Green Industrial Deal will continue until 2027. Heating and Cooling strategies were also in the presentation agenda in reference to The Affordable Energy Plan initiative which will require support at national and local level due to policy interlinkages, complexity and local involvement. This interlinkage has several pillars to be considered including finance, infrastructural needs, value chains, consumer behavior and efficient business models. The support of the Electrification Action Plan to address stagnant level of electricity in energy consumption was also deemed an important agenda item by the policy officer. Lastly, the PO drew attention to the new workflows of the SET Plan in regard to the transition from a Steering Group to a formal Commission Expert Group.

As an important pillar in engaging research and industry entities in support of concentrated and non-concentrated solar thermal activities across Europe, Christina Trueba, the Concentrated Solar Thermal Technologies Implementation Working Group (CST/IWG) Chair highlighted the current outputs and

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the new structuring of the CST-IWG group. The current SET Plan countries include Spain (Chair), Germany, Italy, Portugal, Türkiye, Belgium, Cyprus, Greece and France. The expansion of the scope of CST IWG, to address also non-concentrated solar thermal technologies (NCST) was also mentioned to encompass the whole solar thermal energy sector, given the heat and energy needs of industrial processes and households and the adequate R&I activities needed to foster further collaboration. Lastly emphasis to the new SET Plan governance structure was mentioned which will affect the roles and responsibilities of the following contributing entities :SG, IWGs, ETIPs, EERA, Task Forces.

Project partner Ricardo Sanchez Moreno from CIEMAT, has highlighted the progress on the CST Implementation Plan, mentioning the significant progress made toward the CST implementation Plan targets especially in cost reduction, efficiency improvements and integration of solar fuels and industrial heat applications. National and EU funding support was highlighted with Germany, Spain and Italy having the greatest number of projects and also receiving the most funding portraying institutional and country commitments to enhance CST technology. CST Implementation Plan Targets include 1) cost reduction of electricity to values below 15 c€/kWh in Southern Europe locations by 2025, targeting below 10 c€/kWh by 2030, 2) development of next generation CSP/STE technology (NEXTGEN) to achieve at least 3 points of increase in the overall power plant efficiency from the reference value 39.4 percent to 42.4 percent by 2025, 3) integration of at least one First of a Kind (FOAK) technology in the energy system by 2025, demonstrating either the cost reduction or the efficiency increase 4) Thermal energy cost reduction for industrial process heat applications to be below 3 c€/kWh by 2030 for the same Southern Europe locations as the target 1, with process temperatures higher than 200 °C and 25 years' lifetime and 5) Demonstration of 24/7 economically viable solar thermal baseload production of green hydrogen and other solar fuels by 2030.

Project coordinator, Peter Heller from DLR, presented the R&I workshop outputs from the four workshops: a) Cross-Cutting Materials Challenges of Renewable Energy Technologies, b) Hybridization of CST with Other Renewable Technologies, c) Meteorology for Renewable Energy Technologies and the d) Future Energy Mix with 100% Decarbonization Level. The main concerns within the materials topic was material corrosion and material recycling. Main hybridization concerns included co-generation of power and heat, financing parameters and choice of subsystems and operational strategies to support hybrid plants and dispatchability. Meteorology implications were discussed at several levels including quality of DNI measurements and reliability of meteo-data. Moreover, effects of grid stability, development of cost-sensors for small scale/low-cost CST plants and effect of climate change on power output was also discussed. Lastly, for the R&I on energy mix options, the advantages of CST were relayed. These include independence from critical materials and full production of technology components in Europe. Storage options using batteries for PV and wind technologies is still deemed uncertain, proving the advantage of CST. The importance of credible pipeline projects were emphasized for developing the CSP industry in Europe.

Project partner Konstantinos Genikomsakis from ESTELA showcased the industry workshop outputs for PV, Biomass, Heat Pumps, Geothermal and Energy Storage. The presentation drew attention to the SWOT (Strengths-Weaknesses-Opportunities-Threats), as well as the core technology needs and R&I focus for each renewable energy pairing and key investment opportunities for sustained technology development. Key takeaways for the technology pairings include : a) PV/CST: Complementary technologies rather than competing technologies. Hybridization would allow lowering levelized cost of energy (LCOE) and higher capacity factors in comparison to singular

initiatives b) Biomass/CST: Integration complexity were addressed as challenges to find financing and circumvent the technology pairing complexities. However, clean, reliable and secure energy generation is possible with extended collaboration between stakeholders. c) Heat Pumps/CST: The pairing offers a great potential for efficient renewable energy, particularly for industrial and district heat applications. The importance of scaling up demonstration projects will be critical in driving the innovation potential and unlocking the economic and environmental benefits. d) Geothermal/CST: The geothermal RE pairing offers improvement for electricity production, industrial process heat and district heating/cooling to improve energy security, grid stability and decarbonization. Viability in different locations and conditions and supportive policy frameworks were among the needs addressed to improve the hybridization potential. Lastly e) Energy Storage/CST: Holds a critical role in improving Europe's clean transition with improved grid stability, 24/7 energy availability and industrial decarbonization approaches. It is among the more mature and versatile hybridization solutions to effectively integrate other RE technologies.

Project partner Hande Eryilmaz from GUNAM delivered the work on the SSH aspects of the CST ecosystem and its hybridization potential through the lens of cross-sectoral collaboration, technology adoption, social acceptance, just transition, energy poverty and gender aspects. The presentation reflected the alignment with core EU documents and ended with suggestions for short-medium-long term implications under social, economic and policy aspects for CST technology.

The afternoon session was enriched with a roundtable discussion to highlight the needs for EU-Cross technology cooperation. The discussions highlighted the importance of a technology being mainstream and the importance of hybridization in complementing weaknesses in a technology. The event was finalized with closing remarks by project coordinator Peter Heller, representing DLR.

CST4ALL Coordinator

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CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (ES)

ITALIAN NATIONAL AGENCY FOR NEW TECHNOLOGIES,
ENERGY AND SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

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